

GOUT AND ITS ASSOCIATION WITH BIOCHEMICAL MARKERS

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Introduction: Gout is a chronic metabolic disorder that arises due to persistent hyperuricemia, a condition where uric acid levels in the blood are abnormally elevated. This leads to the deposition of monosodium urate crystals in tissues and joints, causing acute and chronic inflammation. While the condition is primarily recognized for its impact on joints, it can also result in systemic complications, including gouty nephropathy—a form of kidney dysfunction caused by the prolonged accumulation of uric acid crystals in the renal tubules.

This thesis aims to explore the connection between gout and specific biochemical markers, such as serum creatinine and uric acid levels, which play a crucial role in both the progression and diagnosis of the disease. Furthermore, the study delves into the risk factors that lead to kidney complications, with a particular focus on older patients who are more susceptible to severe forms of gout and nephropathy.

Data: 1 A total of 46 patients with confirmed gout were included in this study, comprising 44 males and 3 females. This gender disparity highlights the significantly higher prevalence of gout among males, likely due to hormonal and lifestyle factors.

2. Age Range: The age range of the participants was between 40 and 70 years. Notably, older individuals (aged over 50) accounted for a substantial proportion of severe cases, underlining the role of age as a contributing factor to disease progression.

3. Gouty Nephropathy: Of the 46 patients, 20 males were diagnosed with gouty nephropathy, representing 43.5% of the study population. Among these, 15 individuals were older than 50, suggesting a strong correlation between advancing age and the risk of kidney complications. 4. Biochemical Analysis Results: Creatinine Levels: 20 patients had serum creatinine levels above 130 mmol/l (normal creatinine levels for males: 62-106 mmol/l, females: 53-97 mmol/l).

Uric Acid Levels: All patients had elevated uric acid levels, confirming the diagnosis of gout.

Patients over 50 years old: For those aged over 50, serum creatinine levels were higher than 130 mmol/l, and uric acid levels exceeded 7 mg/dl (normal uric acid levels for men: 3.5-7.2 mg/dl, women: 2.6-6.0 mg/dl).

Analysis: 1. Creatinine Levels: Elevated serum creatinine serves as a critical marker for renal dysfunction, reflecting a reduced glomerular filtration rate (GFR). Among the study participants, patients over the age of 50 exhibited disproportionately high creatinine levels, suggesting that age-related renal decline exacerbates the impact of chronic hyperuricemia. The data underscores the importance of routine monitoring of serum creatinine to assess and manage kidney health in gout patients. 2. Uric Acid Levels: Hyperuricemia is a hallmark of gout and plays a pivotal role in the pathogenesis of the disease. Persistently elevated uric acid levels lead to the formation of monosodium urate crystals, which not only trigger joint inflammation but also obstruct renal tubules, resulting in gouty nephropathy. Patients aged over 50 showed significantly higher uric acid levels, pointing to a more aggressive disease course and increased susceptibility to renal damage. 3. Age as a Risk Factor The findings highlight a direct relationship between advancing age and the severity of gout and its complications. Older patients are more likely to experience renal impairment due to the combined effects of chronic hyperuricemia, age-related physiological changes, and comorbidities such as hypertension and diabetes.

Clinical Implications: The relationship between age and biochemical markers shows that gout and gouty nephropathy are more prevalent in older patients, making early detection and management crucial to prevent further complications.

Conclusion: Elevated serum creatinine and uric acid levels are critical biochemical markers for the diagnosis and progression of gout and its renal complications. The study emphasizes that older patients, particularly those over the age of 50, are at a significantly higher risk of developing gouty nephropathy. This underscores the necessity of early detection, routine monitoring, and comprehensive management strategies to improve clinical outcomes and prevent irreversible kidney damage.

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